

MECHANICAL COMPOSITION OF IRRIGATED SOILS OF THE LOWER AMUDARYA BASIN AND CHANGES UNDER IRRIGATION

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Abstract. *The article presents information on the amount of physical clay and physical sand particles that make up the elements of the mechanical composition of irrigated meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils of Chimboy and Shumanay districts. The following results were obtained as a result of the study of the mechanical composition of meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils distributed on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya. These soils are rich in large dust fractions, and small amounts of large sand and medium sand fractions were recorded. According to the mechanical composition, it was observed that light sandy and heavy sandy soils predominate, and sand, medium sandy and light clay areas were also noted. Among the studied soils, we can say that Ch-B, sample 4, which has been irrigated for a long time, has medium loamy upper layers, and light sandy loamy lower layers, is the best in terms of fertility and chemical properties. In general, it is characterized by the characteristic features and their complexity, as well as dramatic changes in the mechanical composition of the soil profile. In some cases, it is noted that sandy layers alternate with silty layers, and sometimes sandy layers alternate with silty layers. The sharp fluctuations of the mechanical fractions in this form are explained in connection with the sharp and contradictory changes in the lithology of the alluvial deposits. The mechanical composition of the soil is considered its important property, and according to it, soils are divided into different categories. Determining the mechanical composition of soil layers and studying its genesis (origin) is of great importance, since its mechanical composition depends not only on the composition of the parent rock, but also on the soil formation processes occurring in the soil.*

Keywords: *meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils, mechanical structure, mechanical elements, light, medium and heavy loams, physical clay and silt particles.*

Introduction: Today, one third of the world's soils are degraded by erosion, leaching of organic matter, alkalization, pollution and other negative processes. A number of decisions have been developed to prevent such processes, maintain and increase soil fertility.

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 10, 2022 "On measures to create an effective system of combating land degradation" No. PD-277 on preventing land degradation in Uzbekistan and eliminating its consequences important tasks are defined. In this regard, it is important to deeply study the characteristics of irrigated lands in different soil and climate conditions of our republic, to determine the evolutionary changes occurring in the soil, to

restore and increase soil fertility, and to carry out fundamental and innovative research [1]. This decision includes forecast indicators aimed at reducing and preventing land degradation processes in 2022-2025, reducing the area of existing saline soils from 1902.3 thousand hectares to 1809.0 thousand hectares in 2022 planned. The area of land with less than 1% humus reserve is planned to decrease from 2413.7 thousand hectares to 1524.3 thousand hectares [2].

Land degradation poses a serious problem for the economic development of all Central Asian countries, including our Republic, and causes great damage to agriculture. More than 700,000 hectares of dry land in Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Tashkent and Kashkadarya regions are affected by water and irrigation erosion, and more than 15% of irrigated land suffers from wind erosion. According to the information provided by the international organization FAO, about 60% of the world's land area has been degraded [6-9pp, 3].

Combating land degradation in our republic and mitigating its negative consequences, preventing desertification and drying, salinization and erosion processes in the regions, preserving biodiversity, maintaining and increasing soil fertility, restoring degraded and deflated lands, advanced scientific developments in this direction and One of the urgent problems of today is the more effective use of soils in irrigated farming zones and regions for agricultural purposes and soil conservation based on the wide use of innovations. Currently, in the conditions of Karakalpakstan, we can find a lot of land that has been deflated.

In comparison with the irrigated soils of the middle and southern parts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the soil cover of the Aral Sea region is the progress of desertification and our research is aimed at studying the state of the soils in this region, changing such negative phenomena as degradation, dehumification, decrease in nutrient content, reduction of secondary salinization processes, etc. .d., that there is a need for their careful study.

Research conducted in recent years has shown that soil salinization and alkalization have increased and the content of humus and nutrients has decreased significantly.

Research object and methods: Old and newly irrigated meadow-alluvial and takyrl-like meadow soils, widespread in Chimboy and Shumanay districts on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya, are the object of research. Generally accepted genetic-geographical, profile-geochemical methods were used in the research [19-26pp, 4]. The mechanical composition of the soil was carried out according to N.A. Kachinsky's modified hydrometer and pipette methods [196-198pp, 5].

The obtained results and their analysis:

Irrigated takyrl-like meadow soils, which underwent the process of desertification in ancient times, are scattered in small areas on the ancient surface of the Amudarya delta in the remote parts of the oases of Kungirov, Chimboy, Takhtakopir and Qonlikol districts. Groundwater 2-3 m. oscillating between Barren soils have previously passed the hydromorphic stage during evolutionary development, and they still have residual signs of hydromorphism, and now this process is developing rapidly. Oxidation-reduction processes are activated in the lower part of the section. According to the mesanic composition, the soil section is sharply layered and uneven: from heavy loam and clay to sandy loam, the arable layer of 27-30 cm is mainly heavy and medium loam, rarely light loam and loam. In soils with a mechanical composition of heavy sand, an 8-10 cm thick compacted subsoil layer was formed. In the lower part of the section, there are signs of old and increasing hydromorphism in the form of rust-brown spots. The soils are weak and moderately saline

If we compare the soil morphology with the previous years, we have observed that seepage waters fall to the lower layer, where the level of seepage waters was 1.5-2 m in previous years, but by today it has decreased to 2.5-3 m [42-46 pp.6]

Depending on the age of irrigation and geomorphological regions, in old irrigated takyr-meadow soils the volumetric mass was 1.45–1.55 g/cm³, in meadow-takyr soils - 1.44–1.71 g/cm³, in newly developed desert- sandy soils - 1.44–1.48 g/cm³. These soils are highly compacted, sometimes very compacted. Also, in old-irrigated meadow soils, the volumetric mass from the upper horizons down the soil profile is, respectively, 1.37–1.50 and 1.49–1.47 g/cm³, in newly irrigated takyr (takyr-like) soils -1.33– 1.56 g/cm³ and soils are considered to be medium to highly compacted. Newly irrigated takyr-meadow soils are the least compacted by volumetric mass throughout the entire territory, where the volumetric mass is 0.97 - 1.31 g/cm³. The specific gravity of the soils of the territory under consideration according to their soil profile ranges from 2.57-2.73 g/cm³, corresponding to low and medium degrees, porosity indicators range from 45–64 % [30p, 6].

The mechanical composition of soils depends on a number of indicators, such as the topography of the place, its mineralogical composition, parent rock, and the level of turbidity of irrigation water used in irrigated agriculture. Mechanical composition is important in knowing the chemical, physical, physico-chemical and other properties of soils, determining their productivity. The solid part of the soil consists of mechanical particles of various sizes. They are rocks, fragments of minerals, as well as various mineral, organic and organo-mineral compounds formed in the process of soil formation. The solid part of the soil consists of mechanical particles of various sizes. They are rocks, fragments of minerals, as well as various mineral, organic and organo-mineral compounds formed in the process of soil formation. Fractions of mechanical particles in the soil have different properties, therefore, the mechanical composition of the soil largely describes its most important properties, i.e., porosity, water-physical properties, thermal properties, soil structure, chemical composition, absorption capacity, biological activity and productivity. [66-77pp, 7].

Fig. 1. Mechanical composition of newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils, %

mechanical analysis of the 6th and 3rd samples in the Qamishariq massif of Chimboy district are as follows: the amount of large sand (>0.25) particles along the soil profile is 0.2-2.8%, medium sand (0.25-0.1) is 0.1 - 1.4%, fine sand particles (0.1 - 0.05) 3.1-32.9%, large dust (0.05-0.01) particles 21.6-55.2%, medium dust (0.01-0.005) particles 7.6-34.5%, fine dust (0.005-0.001) 2.5-28.0%, clay (<0.001) particles 0.5-20.5% and physical clay particles (<0.01) fluctuated between 10.6-74.6% (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Mechanical composition of old irrigated takyr-like meadow soils, %

The results of the analysis in samples 4 and 2 of the Bozatau massif of Chimboy district show that the amount of large sand particles (>0.25) along the soil profile is 0.4-1.2%, medium sand (0.25-0.1) is 0.1 - 2.0%, fine sand particles (0.1 - 0.05) 12.3-42.6%, large dust (0.05-0.01) particles 37.3-58.8%, medium dust (0.01-0.005) particles 5.9-21.1%, fine dust (0.005-0.001) 1.6-14.1%, clay (<0.001) particles 0.3-6.5% and physical clay particles (<0.01) ranged from 11.6 to 46.6% (Fig. 4).

On the territory of the Khojeyli region, there are mainly old irrigated, partially newly irrigated meadow alluvial and newly developed meadow soils, differing in mechanical composition. The upper horizon of the studied soils (0-20-30 cm) is mainly medium and heavy loam, sometimes light loams are found. The lower soil horizons vary from light loamy to sandy loam and sand. Judging by the mechanical composition of genetic soil horizons, it can be noted that the studied soils have good water-physical properties and water permeability[307-309pp, 8].

Fig. 4. Mechanical composition of old irrigated takyr-like meadow soils, %

The obtained data show that the amount of physical clay in the second layer of the soil profile (Sh-Sh, cross-section 1) was 24.8%, and we can see that the amount of physical clay increases to 61.9% as it deepens. In another soil sample (Ch-Q, sample 4), we can see a reduction in physical clay content from 46.6% to 11.6% in the deep part of the profile. Such a sharp fluctuation in the amount of mechanical fractions is related to the sharply changing lithology of alluvial deposits.

The mechanical composition of the soil is considered its important property, and according to it, soils are divided into different categories. Determining the mechanical composition of soil layers and studying its genesis (origin) is of great importance, since its mechanical composition depends not only on the composition of the parent rock, but also on the soil formation processes occurring in the soil. The distribution of clay particles across the soil cross-section is considered a good indicator indicating the presence of secondary clay mineral formation (soil turbidity) in the soil. The number of silt particles in silt layers increases compared to the soil-forming rock, and this becomes the basis for the identification of metamorphic layers in the soil section. The nature of the distribution of soil particles in the soil also indicates the speed and qualitative direction of the soil formation process[59-60p, 9].

Conclusion. The following results were obtained as a result of the study of the mechanical composition of meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils distributed on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya. These soils are rich in large dust fractions, and small amounts of large sand and medium sand fractions were recorded. According to the mechanical composition, it was observed that light sandy and heavy sandy soils predominate, and sand, medium sandy and light clay areas were also noted. The structure of the lithological profile is characterized by sharp layering and different mechanical composition. Among the studied soils, we can say that Ch-B,

sample 4, which has been irrigated for a long time, has medium loamy upper layers, and light sandy loamy lower layers, is the best in terms of fertility and chemical properties.

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